

THE MECHANISMS OF PROTEINURIA AND ITS SIGNIFICANCE AS AN OUTCOME INDICATOR IN CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE

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Abstract: Chronic kidney diseases (CKD) share common pathological mechanisms that, regardless of the initial cause, lead to glomerular hyperfiltration, proteinuria, progressive renal scarring, and loss of kidney function. Substantial experimental evidence highlights the pivotal role of proteinuria in accelerating CKD progression to end-stage renal failure through various pathways, including the induction of tubular chemokine expression and complement activation. These processes trigger interstitial inflammatory cell infiltration and persistent fibrogenesis. Proteinuria is widely acknowledged as a key marker of CKD severity and a predictor of future declines in glomerular filtration rate. Furthermore, reducing proteinuria consistently correlates with slower renal function decline in both diabetic and non-diabetic kidney disease. Emerging data also reveal a link between proteinuria levels and cardiovascular risk, extending even to levels of urinary albumin excretion previously considered within the 'normal' range. Thus, proteinuria serves as a valuable surrogate endpoint in clinical trials for CKD and an important therapeutic target for reno- and cardioprotective strategies.

Keywords: biomarker, cardiovascular, chronic kidney disease, proteinuria.

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) affects approximately 5–7% of the global population and poses a significant health burden, with affected individuals facing higher risks of hospitalization and cardiovascular disease compared to their peers of similar age and gender in the general population. A cohort study involving nearly 1.3 million participants revealed that unadjusted mortality rates following myocardial infarction were markedly higher in individuals with CKD compared to those with pre-existing cardiovascular disease or diabetes [1]. Due to its largely asymptomatic nature, CKD often goes undiagnosed, with four out of five affected individuals unaware of their condition as they progressively lose renal function over time. Tragically, half of CKD patients succumb to cardiovascular events before reaching end-stage renal disease (ESRD), and nearly two-thirds of patients initiating dialysis die within five years—a life expectancy worse than that seen in patients with heart failure or many common cancers.

The substantial burden of CKD, coupled with its associated costs, adverse health outcomes, and reduced productivity, underscores its status as a global public health challenge [2]. This problem is even more acute in low-resource settings, where ESRD often represents a "death sentence" due to limited access to dialysis or kidney transplantation, leading to the deaths of nearly one million ESRD patients annually.

While advances in CKD prevention and management have improved patient outcomes in recent decades, the number of individuals progressing to ESRD remains alarmingly high [3]. Experimental studies have spurred the development of new therapeutic options, yet

disappointingly few nephroprotective treatments have reached clinical application. The slow, progressive nature of CKD adds to the difficulty of designing clinical trials with definitive endpoints such as the need for renal replacement therapy or mortality. Although the doubling of serum creatinine is recognized by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA) as a surrogate endpoint, its utility in clinical trials is limited, as several years are often required for this outcome to manifest.

Proteinuria as a Key Risk Factor in Renal Disease Progression

Proteinuria is a well-established risk factor for the progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD) in both diabetic and non-diabetic populations. A large-scale screening of 107,192 individuals in Okinawa, Japan, identified proteinuria as the strongest predictor of end-stage renal disease (ESRD) over a 10-year period in the general population. Similarly, in the Ramipril Efficacy in Nephropathy (REIN) trial, which included 274 patients with non-diabetic chronic nephropathies and clinical proteinuria, urinary protein excretion was the only baseline variable significantly correlated with the rate of glomerular filtration rate (GFR) decline and progression to ESRD. When stratified by baseline proteinuria levels, patients in the lowest tertile had slower rates of CKD progression and lower risk of ESRD compared to those in the middle and highest tertiles. Consistent findings were observed in the Modification of Diet in Renal Disease (MDRD) study and the African-American Study of Kidney Disease and Hypertension (AASK), where higher baseline proteinuria predicted a more rapid decline in GFR in non-diabetic CKD patients.

The same pattern is observed in diabetic patients. The UK Prospective Diabetes Study 74 demonstrated that even increases in urinary albumin within the normal range were independently associated with the future development of microalbuminuria (urine albumin excretion of 30–300 mg/24 h) or renal impairment in type 2 diabetic patients without baseline albuminuria. Furthermore, in patients with diabetic nephropathy, the baseline urinary albumin-to-creatinine ratio was identified as a strong independent predictor of ESRD in both the Reduction of Endpoints in NIDDM with the Angiotensin II Antagonist Losartan (RENAAL) study and the Irbesartan in Diabetic Nephropathy Trial (IDNT).

Proteinuria's Pathogenic Role in Renal Function Decline

Experimental studies have provided crucial insights into the mechanisms underlying the progression of chronic kidney disease (CKD). It is now well recognized that chronic proteinuric nephropathies, regardless of their primary cause, share a common feature: a loss of selectivity in the glomerular barrier, allowing excessive protein filtration. In an experimental model of renal mass reduction via five-sixths nephrectomy, the remaining glomeruli undergo hypertrophy, accompanied by a disproportionate reduction in the tone of afferent arterioles compared to efferent ones. These adaptations result in increased glomerular capillary hydraulic pressure and elevated single-nephron filtration rates. While initially compensatory, these changes eventually inflict progressive damage on the remaining intact nephrons. Elevated intraglomerular capillary pressure stretches the glomerular capillaries, impairing their filtering capacity and leading to the loss of larger molecules, such as proteins, into the urine. Recent findings have identified a direct link between podocyte detachment, endothelial cell fenestration, and albuminuria in patients with type 2 diabetes. Similar correlations observed in type 1 diabetes demonstrate that these structural

abnormalities worsen alongside the classic histological features of diabetic kidney disease, establishing a connection between glomerular injury, albuminuria, and renal scarring.

These findings support the hypothesis that tubulointerstitial damage is mediated by the direct toxicity of filtered proteins. Excessive protein loading of podocytes has been implicated in their progressive injury, with subsequent release of transforming growth factor- β (TGF- β), which induces mesangial cell differentiation into myofibroblasts. In vitro studies have shown that proximal tubular cells exposed to plasma proteins such as albumin, IgG, and transferrin release profibrotic and pro-inflammatory molecules, including endothelin-1 (ET-1), RANTES, and osteopontin. Protein overloading of human proximal tubular cells also stimulates the synthesis of fractalkine, a membrane-anchored chemokine that promotes mononuclear cell adhesion via the CX3CR1 receptor. Increased fractalkine gene expression has been observed in the kidneys of mice with protein overload proteinuria, with the protein product localized predominantly in the basal regions of tubular epithelial cells.

Reducing Proteinuria Slows Renal Disease Progression

Clinical trials have consistently demonstrated the renoprotective effects of reducing proteinuria. The MDRD study established that proteinuria reduction achieved through antihypertensive therapy was associated with a slower rate of glomerular filtration rate (GFR) decline. Importantly, the degree of renal protection conferred by blood pressure reduction was closely linked to the baseline level of proteinuria.

The REIN study further supported this concept by investigating the hypothesis that angiotensin-converting enzyme (ACE) inhibitors could provide superior renoprotection compared to other antihypertensive agents due to their antiproteinuric effects. In this study, patients with chronic nephropathies were randomized to receive ramipril or conventional antihypertensive therapy to maintain diastolic blood pressure at or below 90 mmHg. Despite achieving similar blood pressure control in both groups, ACE inhibitor therapy resulted in significantly greater reductions in proteinuria and a 50% lower risk of progression to ESRD. Patients with higher baseline proteinuria levels derived greater benefit from treatment, but regardless of the initial proteinuria level, short-term reductions in proteinuria were strongly correlated with slower rates of GFR decline and lower long-term risk of ESRD.

Similar findings have been observed in diabetic kidney disease. In type 1 diabetics with overt nephropathy, enalapril was shown to slow GFR decline more effectively than β -adrenoceptor blockers, despite comparable blood pressure control. Another trial involving 409 type 1 diabetics revealed that captopril reduced the risk of reaching the combined endpoint of doubling serum creatinine, ESRD, or death compared to placebo, with slower progression linked to greater reductions in proteinuria.

In type 2 diabetics, large clinical trials have shown that proteinuria reduction through angiotensin receptor blockers is associated with reduced incidence of serum creatinine doubling and lower risk of ESRD. Post hoc analyses from numerous randomized clinical trials have consistently found that short-term reductions in proteinuria are invariably associated with slower GFR decline and decreased progression to ESRD in the long term. These findings underscore the critical role of proteinuria reduction as a therapeutic target in slowing CKD progression.

Proteinuria as a Cardiovascular Risk Factor

In addition to its role in renal disease progression, proteinuria is a significant risk factor for cardiovascular events and mortality in both diabetic and non-diabetic populations. Patients with proteinuria face an elevated risk of cardiovascular events, cardiovascular-related deaths, and all-cause mortality. Proteinuria has also been linked to myocardial changes in the left ventricle, a higher incidence of stroke, and an increased risk of atherosclerotic events in the peripheral vasculature.

The RENAAL study, which included 1,513 patients with type 2 diabetes randomized to receive either losartan or placebo, demonstrated that each 50% reduction in albuminuria corresponded to an 18% reduction in cardiovascular risk and a 27% reduction in heart failure risk. Similar findings were reported in the LIFE trial, where reductions in albuminuria over time were associated with a lower risk of the primary composite cardiovascular endpoint. In both studies, greater reductions in proteinuria not only slowed renal disease progression but also significantly reduced cardiovascular events. Consistent results were observed in the IDNT trial, which included type 2 diabetes patients with overt nephropathy.

These findings highlight the dual reno- and cardioprotective benefits of interventions that reduce urinary albumin or total protein excretion. Proteinuria and albuminuria are therefore highly sensitive and reliable surrogate endpoints for monitoring and predicting the effectiveness of treatments in both clinical and research settings.

Conclusion

Surrogate endpoints for renal failure are crucial for evaluating new treatments in patients with chronic kidney disease (CKD), whose condition typically progresses slowly and asymptotically. Proteinuria directly contributes to renal disease progression and is widely accepted as an indicator of the severity of glomerulopathy. Both population-based studies and controlled trials have demonstrated that proteinuria predicts a decline in glomerular filtration rate (GFR) and the onset of end-stage renal disease (ESRD). Reducing proteinuria consistently leads to a slower decline in renal function in both diabetic and non-diabetic patients with significant proteinuria. More importantly, lowering proteinuria and preserving kidney function also results in better cardiovascular outcomes. Therefore, proteinuria should be regarded as an important surrogate endpoint for clinical trials in proteinuric renal diseases and a key target for cardiovascular protection.

Although proteinuria has not yet been officially recognized as a surrogate endpoint by the FDA or the European Medicines Agency (EMA) for CKD treatment trials, the compelling evidence has sparked a productive discussion among top nephrologists and FDA officials regarding its qualification as a surrogate marker.

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